

Green Marketing Strategies : Paradigms and Assessment

Adnan Jamil

Lecturer, Department of Leadership and Management Studies,
National Defence University, Islamabad, Pakistan.

**Muhammad
Zia-ur-Rehman**

Assistant Professor, Department of Leadership and Management
Studies, National Defence University, Islamabad, Pakistan.
Email: drziaemail@gmail.com

Abstract

The current study also attempts to contribute significantly in this regard, as it attempts to map relationships between value systems and attitude towards green buying behavior. This study postulates that Environmental Value (EnV) forms the GA, which endorses CBB. After a careful literature

Key Words

Green Consumption values,
Environmental Values,
Attitude towards Green
Products, Consumer Buying
Behavior and Value Attitude
Behavior Hierarchy Theory

review it has been revealed that very limited studies have attempted to map this relationship thread lending credence to the current study. The results indicate that the correlation coefficient achieved a value of 0 .275 0 significant at a P-value of 0.001. The Cronbach's α value achieved for the EnV is 0.747 which is also significant, indicating that the overall results endorse the postulate of the current research that, EnV is also a principle variable other than CV to map CBB for the case of mapping green buying behavior.*

Introduction

“Discussion on ecological matters has steadily increased in the course of recent years meanwhile the start of Earth Day. More than 70 percent of Americans declared that they were in support of natural environment protection and 49 percent said they would stay away from buying items that are conceivably destructive to the environment (Hueber 1991). Marketers have positively responded to purchasers' environmental awareness by developing environment-friendly merchandises (Kohl 1990). Environment-friendly behavior dictates very personal endeavors to restrain from activities which may be unsafe to the usual physical settings of nature. However, just a couple of "green" items have been successful (Reitman 1991) in spite of the tremendous dominant part of buyers revealing that their buying was subjective by ecological apprehensions”(Chase and Smith 1992).

The purpose of this study is to test a model that clarifies the potential impact of ‘values system’ on attitude towards green products and how this attitude affects the green purchase behavior. The study is thus composed of two major parts. Part one – to study the impact of value system on attitude and in part two to study the impact of attitude towards green purchase behavior. The findings would help in understanding the basic drives in green buying behavior.

Literature Review

Value Attitude Behavior Hierarchy (VABH) by Homer and Kahle's (1988) is preferred as the conceptual structure for this study. VABH elaborates the particular consumers' behavior patterns indirectly effected by the consumers' abstract values i.e. directly and more specifically influencing the attitudes of the consumer which play a role in the shaping of the consumers' behavior (Homer et al, 1988). In the present days' social psychology, the attitude is interpreted as the personal assessment about particular product (e.g. Fabrigar et al, 2010). Consumers' attitudes are observed as a major precursor of behavior and are therefore an essential element of different theoretical models, such as the theory of reasoned action (TRA) (Fishbein et al, 1975) and the theory of planned behavior (TPB) (Ajzen, 1991). Moreover the attitude-behavior relationship, which is crucial to elucidate the Attitude Behavior-Gap, the Value Attitude Behavior Hierarchy also enlightens the different dynamic aspects of the attitude behavioral gap which are influenced by an individual's values. In the previous researches of eco-friendly consumerism and social psychology, the key determinant of behavior frequently comes into light are the values of the consumer (e.g. Dunlap and Riley, 1983; Urien et al, 2011; Yigitcanlar and Lönnqvist et al., 2013; Jacobs et al, 2018).

Functional Value

A consumers' notion of a product in terms of price, quality, durability, dependability, and reliability is measured through FV, i.e., the products' utilitarian, functional or physical performance drives the consumer value. The main driver of consumer choice are these factors which are combinedly known as the function value of the consumer (Sheth et al., 1991). Price and quality are the two facades of the FV by Sweeney and Soutar (2001), who measures durable goods by using PERVAL scale. Bei and Simpson (1995) argued that during the buying decision process of the recycled products were closely evaluated by the consumer on the basis of their price and quality. The FV (price) is influenced by the purchase of green products (Finch, 2006). According to a study conducted Taiwan by Lin and Huang (2012) find out that environmentally friendly products can be sold to some consumers who are willing to pay premium prices. They claim that green product consumer choice behavior does not have a significant relationship with FV (price). But, In India it was established that sustainable consumption behavior has a positive effect by the FV (price) (Biswas & Roy, 2015) and in Portugal, on green product purchase behavior (Gonçalves, Lourenço & Silva, 2016). This leads to the following hypothesis:

H1: ATGP is positively influenced by the FVof the green product consumer."

Social Value

The observed function of a product or service linked with particular social, demographic, socioeconomic or cultural groups by SV(Sheth et al., 1991). There is a substantial impact on green consumer behavior by the extent to which a product is seen to improve self-image of the consumer (Finch, 2006) it is all connected with self-image (Sweeney & Soutar, 2001). Consumers' insight of risk can be significantly abridged by what they identify as expert opinions;they need more information when they faced with a social risk to prevent a negative consequence(Aqueveque, 2006). The green product consumer choice behavior in Taiwan, have no positive significant effect from the social values argued by Lin and Huang (2012). However in India, Biswas & Roy (2015)observed that sustainable consumption behavior is positively affected by social values of the consumer (Biswas & Roy, 2015) same as in Portugal on the green product purchase behavior (Gonçalves et al., 2016). This leads to the following hypothesis:

H2: ATGP is positively influenced by the SVof the green product consumer.

Conditional Value

The consumption of a product or service is linked with explicit conditions when rises (Wang, Liao & Yang, 2013) and the observed function resulting from a given situation or set of conditions is the CVof the consumer(Sheth et al., 1991). Green consumer behavior is intensely influenced by the CV of the consumer (Lin & Huang, 2012). The purchase of green products can be affected by the sudden changes in situational variables (particular circumstances) (Saxena & Khandelwal, 2010; Gadenne, Sharma, Kerr & Smith, 2011). In India, sustainable consumption behavior is observed to be positively affected by the consumers' CV (Biswas & Roy, 2015) and in Portugal on the green product purchase behavior (Gonçalves et al., 2016). This leads to the following hypothesis:

H3: ATGP is positively influenced by the CV of the green product consumer.

Epistemic Value

A product or service to stimulate inquisitiveness or deliver newness to the products' observed usefulness to the consumer is the aptitude of the consumers' EpV (Sheth et al., 1991). Green product consumer purchase behavior can be provoked by the consumers' craving to acquirefurther about a product's characteristics (Tanner & Kast, 2003). To elucidate a problem, for example, the consumers' craving to know further encourages thepursuingnewnessin the product, (Lin & Huang, 2012). Consumer purchase behavior can be posh by the deficiency of information related to green products (Ginsberg & Bloom, 2004). In India, sustainable consumption behavior is observed to be positively affected by the consumers' EpV (Biswas & Roy, 2015) and in Portugal on the green product purchase behavior (Gonçalves et al., 2016). This leads to the following hypothesis:

H4: ATGP is positively influenced by the EpV of the green product consumer.

Environmental Value

A consumer's attitude in the direction of environmental trepidations such as growing populace, contamination of environment, saving of energy, wastage of resources and the consequence of usage of poisonous chemicals in the air and natural surroundings is measured by EnV (Kim & Choi, 2005). Eco-friendly behavior positively correlated with EnV (Straughan and Roberts 1999). Green consumption patterns are more possible to be embraced by the

consumers as there will be an increase in their environmental apprehensions (Kilbourne & Pickett, 2008; Rex & Baumann, 2007). In India, sustainable consumption behavior is observed to be positively affected by the consumers' EnV (Biswas & Roy, 2015). This leads to the following hypothesis:

H5: ATGP is positively influenced by the EnV of the green product consumer.

Attitude towards Green Products (ATGP)

The research of eco-friendly consumer mindset, as one of the pivotal precursor of perceived behavioral intent, and actual behavior, the occurrence of attitude has been always highlighted. "A learned predisposition to respond in a consistently favorable or unfavorable manner with respect to a given object" (p. 211) the term attitude was defined by the Fishbein et al (1975). In addition to this the purchase choice for product or services is more depending on the behavioral occurrences which embodies; what consumers like and dislike in overall and precise footings (Blackwell et al., 2006). Consequently, overall attitude and explicit attitude will be categorized from the attitude (Sun and Willson, 2008; Tan, 2011; Jaiswal and Kant, 2018). The inclusive inclination to employ in relevant behavior of a group of attitude towards product entails into an over-all attitude; a robust prognosticator of a particular behavior on a specific attitude towards a product (Eagly and Chaiken 1993; Tan 2011; Jaiswal et al 2018). Consequently, particular behavior on the ecological concerns a particular attitude usually preserved as ATGP merchandises or consumption in the eco-friendly customer studies that grasp individual's views or emotional state towards the consumption choice of ecologically beneficial merchandises (Kaiser et al, 2003; Riethmuller et al, 2008; Jaiswal et al., 2018). On the other hand, the compassion of environmental sustainability diverges from the ATGP at behavioral level of green merchandise consumption decision (Kaiser, Wölfling and Fuhrer, 1999; Tan, 2011; Jaiswal et al., 2018). The significance of this particular occurrence with buying intent and consumption behavior for over-all ecological beneficial merchandise broadly, established by several scholars (Chen et al, 2010; Lai et al, 2016; Yadav et al, 2016; Jaiswal et al., 2018). In accumulation, recently in Indian context such essential associations were also authenticated (Paul and Patel, 2016; Yadav et al, 2016; and Kumar and Polonsky, 2017; Jaiswal et al., 2018). Hence it is estimated that high amount of consumer participation in purchase choice of general green products that buyers with more positive ATGP were anticipated, it is also revealed by the literature (Chan et al, 2010; Joshi et al, 2015; Jaiswal et al., 2018)". Therefore current research undertakes to observe the over-all ATGP with the buying behavior for these types of merchandises to authenticate in the setting of Indian context, corresponding with the above debate on this focused substance, the following hypotheses were suggested:

H6: GPB is positively influenced by the consumers' ATGP.

Green Purchase Behavior

The consumption of ecologically friendly products or ecological products which can be 'reusable and 'favorable' to the atmosphere and circumventing such products which damage the environment and humanity is stated to be GPB (Chan, 2001; Mostafa, 2007). Consumers' inclination or intent to buy an ecofriendly merchandises is commonly used term as the consumer behavior for green purchasing and their buying choice for such merchandises in order to benevolent for their ecological sustainability that sooner or later transformed by their cognizant attitude or intention (Joshi et al, 2015; Jaiswal et al., 2018). In the investigation of buyer behavior, intentions, integrated with attitude and subjective norms can define the consumer behavior, it was first revealed by Theory of Reasoned Action (TRA) (Fishbein et al, 1975). Consequently, perceived behavioral control was introduced with the measures of the attitude and norms as an addition to the theoretical framework of the TRA action known as Theory of Planned Behavior (TPB) (Ajzen et al, 1980). In addition to that, Asian and Indian markets embraced wholesome green products which are altering and reshaping the behaviors of the consumers (Hsu Chang and Yansritakul, 2017; Kim et al, 2011; Lai et al, 2016; Yadav et al, 2016; Prakash et al, 2017; Jaiswal et al., 2018). On the Basis of the previous researches and ample works' evaluation, it is an obvious notion that green attitude show a crucial role in the formation the green consumer behavior, as well play major influencer and precursor to the GPB" (Paul and Patel, 2016; Kumar and Polonsky, 2017; Jaiswal et al., 2018). The following hypotheses suggest:

H7: GPB is positively influenced by indirectly by consumers' green value in the mediation of consumers' ATGP.

Theoretical Framework

Methodology

Sampling and Data Collection

Data of 450 respondents were collected from the twin cities of Rawalpindi and Islamabad by using convenience sampling method. 343 valid responses were analyzed to identify the relationships. In this research, green consumer values were measured by twenty-five items scale of Khan et al, (2017). ATGP was consist of two questions based on (Paul et al., 2016; Jaiswal et al., 2018). GPB was measured by four questions of Jaiswal et al, (2018). The constructs were further verified via process regression method.

Results and Analysis

The study undertaken is quantitative in nature. Accordingly, several tests have been applied to test the hypothesis. A survey-based on 31 items questionnaire has been conducted to gather the data. The sample characteristics were made explicit through frequency tables; the reliability of all variables was checked through Cronbach coefficient alpha. As for as construct validity is concerned, the scales have already been used in Pakistani context by Khan et al. (2017). Therefore, there is no need to ensure construct validity (Hadi et al. 2016). Hierarchical multiple regression was applied for undertaking the mediation to ascertain the role of mediator between the predictor and criterion variables, process regression method was also applied for testing the intended hypotheses and to decide the rejection and approval of the suggested assumptions

Sample Characteristics Analysis

Sampling characteristics represent gender, age, educational and experience. As presented in the frequency table the sample includes 60.9 percent of the respondents were male whereas 171 participants were within the age bracket of 15-25 years. Most of the participants were holder of Master’s degree with the percentage of 49.56 % out of 343 respondents. Mostly, the respondents have working experience of 1 to 5 years.

Table 1: Sampling Characteristics

	Frequency	Percentage
Gender		
Male	209	60.9%
Female	134	39.1%
Age		
15-25	171	49.8%
26-35	152	44.3%
36-45	19	5.5%
46 above	1	0.29%
Education		
Matriculation	37	10.78%
Bachelors	95	27.69%
Masters	170	49.56%
Masters & Above	41	11.95%
Experience		
1-5	146	42.56%
6-10	98	28.57%
10-15	82	23.90%
15 & Above	17	4.95%

Reliability Analysis of the Scales

Reliability of the 8-item scale of FV is .818. The 5-item scale of EnV is .865 whereas 2 item scale of attitude towards green product is .843. The 4-item scales of social value, CV, EpV and GPB have reliability coefficient of .896, .756, .797 and .816 respectively. According to Camble 1976 the values of Cronbach's Alpha should be >0.7.

Table 2: Reliability Coefficient

Scales	Cronbach's Alpha	No items
FV	.818	8
EnV	.747	5
Social Value	.896	4
CV	.756	4
EpV	.797	4
ATGP	.843	2
GPB	.816	4

Statistical Analysis

To test the proposed relationship drawn in the theoretical framework of the study, SPSS was utilized to run the process regression on the proposed variables to check the model fit. The data gathered from the selected sample was entered in the software and the assumptions of process regression are fulfilled, as shown in table 3.

Table 3: Regression Assumptions

Assumptions	Threshold Point	References	Values of Model		
Durbin Watson	1.5-2.5	Hutcheson & Nick 1999	2.021		
Tolerance Value	Tolerance>0.2	Vasu 1979	CV .555	AGP .496	GPB .770
Variance Inflation Factor	VIF<4	Vasu 1979	1.8	2.017	1.299
Mahal Distance	Cases with Higher Value	Steenkamp et.al 1991	Min .032	Max 12.023	Mean 2.986
Cook's Distance	4/(n-k-1)	Steenkamp et.al 1991	Min .000	Max .075	Mean 0.006

As the table 3 indicates data supported all the preliminary requirements of regression assumptions, so further process regression was carried out to test the proposed hypotheses. The results of all six hypothesis are given in the table 4 below:

Table 4: Hypotheses Results

Hypothesis	Path	β	p-Value	Results
H1	FV \longrightarrow AGP	.597	0.000*	Supported
H2	SV \longrightarrow AGP	.271	0.000*	Supported
H3	CV \longrightarrow AGP	.978	0.000*	Supported
H4	EPV \longrightarrow AGP	.898	0.000*	Supported
H5	EV \longrightarrow AGP	.275	0.001*	Supported
H6	AGP \longrightarrow GPB	.249	0.015*	Supported
H7	CGV \longrightarrow AGP ATGP \longrightarrow GPB	.695	0.000*	Supported

As table 4 indicated hypothesized theoretical framework was evaluated by the help of process regression. Addition to that all hypothesis which is drawn from the proposed theoretical framework were accepted. As suggested, in H1 FV 59.7% influenced the consumers' ATGP and the significance level is also less than 0.05, hence H1 stands accepted. The results also supported H2 i.e. SV is positively related to consumers' ATGP wherein path beta was .271 with the significant p-value. The hypothesis H3 that establishes the CV positively influenced the ATGP was also substantiated wherein path beta was .978 with p value significant. H4 EpV 89.8% influenced the consumers' ATGP and the significance level is also less than 0.05, hence H4 stand accepted. The hypothesis H5 that establishes the EnV positively influenced the ATGP was also substantiated wherein path beta was .375 with p value significant. The results also supported H6 i.e. consumers' ATGP is positively influenced the GPB of the consumer wherein path beta was .249 with significant p value. The over-all value of the adjusted R-square of the model is .484 which explain that predictor variables i.e. is the consumption values and the consumers' ATGP are bringing 48.48% change in the GPB of the consumer. However, the indirect effect (i.e. through mediation of ATGP) is 1.378, path beta is 69.5% and the p value is also significant. The direct effect become insignificant which indicated that full mediation is occurred. So the H7 is also supported by the results and stand accepted.

Conclusion and Recommendations

In this research effort, it was established that both the consumption values and environmental values affect ATGP. ATGP, in turn, affects the GPB. It was found that Pakistani buyers have extremely convincing green buyer esteems. They were found aware of the environmental dangers Pakistan is exposed to from the most recent two decades. These results lead to the major administrative ramifications for the manufacturing organizations to abide by the moral bounds of keeping natural environment unharmed. The greatest advantages of green living are clearly the natural advantages that accompany green, solid living. Activities, for example, reusing, contamination decrease, nature protection and plant and tree development will all make considerably more economical world for us and for our who and what is to come. If we don't begin to contemplate the earth and don't begin to consider its safeguarding as a piece of our everyday life, in a few decades we will be compelled to live in an entirely different world. Simply see what's going on right now with an unnatural weather change and the various ecological changes. So by living green, we will assist our condition with continuing on and to keep up it as it is currently, which will profit not exclusively to the earth itself, however honestly, it will profit to ourselves also.

References

- Ajzen, I. (1991). The theory of planned behavior. *Organizational behavior and human decision processes*, 50(2), 179-211.
- Aqueveque, C. (2006). Extrinsic cues and perceived risk: the influence of consumption situation. *Journal of Consumer Marketing*, 23(5), 237-247.
- Bamberg, S., Ajzen, I., & Schmidt, P. (2003). Choice of travel mode in the theory of planned behavior: The roles of past behavior, habit, and reasoned action. *Basic and applied social psychology*, 25(3), 175-187.
- Bei, L. T., & Simpson, E. M. (1995). The determinants of consumers' purchase decisions for recycled products: an application of acquisition-transaction utility theory. *ACR North American Advances*.
- Biswas, A., & Roy, M. (2015). Green products: an exploratory study on the consumer behaviour in emerging economies of the East. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 87, 463-468.
- Blackwell, R., D'Souza, C., Taghian, M., Miniard, P. & Engel, J. (2006) *Consumer Behaviour*, 1st edn. Thompson Learning Publishers, South Melbourne.
- Camble, H. A. (1976). Adenocarcinoma of the appendix. An unusual case and review. *Camble HA: Dis. colon and rectum*, 19, 621-625.
- Chan, R. Y. (2001). Determinants of Chinese consumers' green purchase behavior. *Psychology & marketing*, 18(4), 389-413.
- Chan, R. Y., & Lau, L. B. (2002). Explaining green purchasing behavior: A cross-cultural study on American and Chinese consumers. *Journal of international consumer marketing*, 14(2-3), 9-40.
- Chen, T. B., & Chai, L. T. (2010). Attitude towards the environment and green products: Consumers' perspective. *Management science and engineering*, 4(2), 27-39.
- Eagly, A. H., & Chaiken, S. (1993). *The psychology of attitudes*. Harcourt Brace Jovanovich College Publishers.
- Fabrigar, L. R., Wegener, D. T., & MacDonald, T. K. (2010). Distinguishing between prediction and influence: Multiple processes underlying attitude-behavior consistency. Then a miracle occurs: Focusing on behavior in social psychological theory and research, 162-185.
- Finch, J. E. (2006). The impact of personal consumption values and beliefs on organic food purchase behavior. *Journal of Food Products Marketing*, 11(4), 63-76.
- Fishbein, M., & Ajzen, I. (1975). *Belief, attitude, intention and behavior: An introduction to theory and research*.
- Gadenne, D., Sharma, B., Kerr, D., & Smith, T. (2011). The influence of consumers' environmental beliefs and attitudes on energy saving behaviours. *Energy policy*, 39(12), 7684-7694.
- Kahn, B. E., & Meyer, R. J. (1991). Consumer multiattribute judgments under attribute-weight uncertainty. *Journal of Consumer Research*, 17(4), 508-522.
- Kaiser, F. G., & Gutscher, H. (2003). The Proposition of a General Version of the Theory of Planned Behavior: Predicting Ecological Behavior I. *Journal of applied social psychology*, 33(3), 586-603.
- Kaiser, F. G., Wöfling, S., & Fuhrer, U. (1999). Environmental attitude and ecological behaviour. *Journal of environmental psychology*, 19(1), 1-19.
- Khan, S. N., & Mohsin, M. (2017). The power of emotional value: Exploring the effects of values on green product consumer choice behavior. *Journal of cleaner production*, 150, 65-74.
- Sheth, J. N., Newman, B. I., & Gross, B. L. (1991). Why we buy what we buy: A theory of consumption values. *Journal of business research*, 22(2), 159-170.
- Kilbourne, W., & Pickett, G. (2008). How materialism affects environmental beliefs, concern, and environmentally responsible behavior. *Journal of Business Research*, 61(9), 885-893.
- Kim, Y., & Choi, S. M. (2005). Antecedents of green purchase behavior: An examination of collectivism, environmental concern, and PCE. *ACR North American Advances*.
- Kumar, P., & Polonsky, M. J. (2017). An analysis of the green consumer domain within sustainability research: 1975 to 2014. *Australasian Marketing Journal (AMJ)*, 25(2), 85-96.
- Lai, C. K., & Cheng, E. W. (2016). Green purchase behavior of undergraduate students in Hong Kong. *The Social Science Journal*, 53(1), 67-76.
- Lee, K. (2008). Opportunities for green marketing: young consumers. *Marketing intelligence & planning*, 26(6), 573-586.
- Lin, P. C., & Huang, Y. H. (2012). The influence factors on choice behavior regarding green products based on the theory of consumption values. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 22(1), 11-18.
- Lönnqvist, J. E., Verkasalo, M., Wichardt, P. C., & Walkowitz, G. (2013). Personal values and prosocial behaviour in strategic interactions: Distinguishing value-expressive from value-ambivalent behaviours. *European Journal of Social Psychology*, 43(6), 554-569.

- McStay, J. R., & Dunlap, R. E. (1983). Male–female differences in concern for environmental quality. *International journal of Women's Studies*.
- MoF. (2018). *Economic Survey of Pakistan*. Islamabad: Ministry of Finance Pakistan.
- Mostafa, M. M. (2007). Gender differences in Egyptian consumers' green purchase behaviour: the effects of environmental knowledge, concern and attitude. *International Journal of Consumer Studies*, 31(3), 220-229.
- Park, H. J., & Rabolt, N. J. (2009). Cultural value, consumption value, and global brand image: A cross-national study. *Psychology & Marketing*, 26(8), 714-735.
- Paul, J., Modi, A., & Patel, J. (2016). Predicting green product consumption using theory of planned behavior and reasoned action. *Journal of retailing and consumer services*, 29, 123-134.
- PBS. (2017). *Population Census Report 2017*. Islamabad: Pakistan Bureau of Statistics.
- Rex, E., & Baumann, H. (2007). Beyond ecolabels: what green marketing can learn from conventional marketing. *Journal of cleaner production*, 15(6), 567-576.
- Riethmuller, S., & Buttriss, G. (2008). *Closing the gap between Pro-environmental Attitudes and Behaviour in Australia*.
- Rokeach, Milton (1973), *The Nature of Human Values*, New York: Free Press
- Saxena, R., & Khandelwal, P. K. (2010). Can green marketing be used as a tool for sustainable growth?: A study performed on consumers in India-An emerging economy.
- Schwartz, S. H. (1992). Universals in the content and structure of values: Theoretical advances and empirical tests in 20 countries. In *Advances in experimental social psychology* (Vol. 25, pp. 1-65). Academic Press.
- Schwartz, S. H. (1994). Beyond individualism/collectivism: New cultural dimensions of values.
- Schwartz, S. H. (2010). Basic values: How they motivate and inhibit prosocial behavior. *Prosocial motives, emotions, and behavior: The better angels of our nature*, 14, 221-241.
- Stern, P. C. (2000). New environmental theories: toward a coherent theory of environmentally significant behavior. *Journal of social issues*, 56(3), 407-424.
- Straughan, R. D., & Roberts, J. A. (1999). Environmental segmentation alternatives: a look at green consumer behavior in the new millennium. *Journal of consumer marketing*, 16(6), 558-575.
- Sun, J., & Willson, V. L. (2008). Assessing general and specific attitudes in human learning behavior: An activity perspective and a multilevel modeling approach. *Educational and Psychological Measurement*, 68(2), 245-261.
- Sweeney, J. C., & Soutar, G. N. (2001). Consumer perceived value: The development of a multiple item scale. *Journal of retailing*, 77(2), 203-220.
- Tan, B. C. (2011). The roles of knowledge, threat, and PCE on green purchase behaviour. *International Journal of Business and Management*, 6(12), 14.
- Tanner, C., & Wölfling Kast, S. (2003). Promoting sustainable consumption: Determinants of green purchases by Swiss consumers. *Psychology & Marketing*, 20(10), 883-902.
- Urien, B., & Kilbourne, W. (2011). Generativity and self-enhancement values in eco-friendly behavioral intentions and environmentally responsible consumption behavior. *Psychology & Marketing*, 28(1), 69-90.
- Wang, H. Y., Liao, C., & Yang, L. H. (2013). What affects mobile application use? The roles of consumption values. *International Journal of Marketing Studies*, 5(2), 11.
- Williams, P., & Soutar, G. N. (2009). Value, satisfaction and behavioral intentions in an adventure tourism context. *Annals of Tourism Research*, 36(3), 413-438.
- Yadav, R., & Pathak, G. S. (2016). Young consumers' intention towards buying green products in a developing nation: Extending the theory of planned behavior. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 135, 732-739.
- Zagata, L. (2012). Consumers' beliefs and behavioural intentions towards organic food. Evidence from the Czech Republic. *Appetite*, 59(1), 81-89.
- Zhao, H. H., Gao, Q., Wu, Y. P., Wang, Y., & Zhu, X. D. (2014). What affects green consumer behavior in China? A case study from Qingdao. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 63, 143-151.